

IMPROVEMENT OF CONTROL MECHANISMS AND REGULATION OF THE TECHNOLOGICAL PROCESS OF GAS DRYING

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Abstract: Gas drying is a crucial process in the natural gas industry to ensure that the gas meets quality standards before distribution. This paper delves into the comprehensive strategies, advanced technologies and regulatory frameworks used to enhance control mechanisms and regulatory compliance in gas drying processes. By focusing on optimizing efficiency, reliability and safety, this study aims to provide valuable insights into improving gas drying operations across various industrial sectors.

Key words: Gas drying, control mechanisms, regulatory compliance, efficiency, reliability, safety.

Introduction: Natural gas processing, petrochemicals, and energy production all rely on gas drying as an important operation. Maintaining the equipment's integrity, preventing corrosion, and meeting the technical requirements of the product requires effective removal of moisture and impurities from the gas. The purpose of this article is to examine the problems faced by gas drying processes and propose strategies for improving control mechanisms and complying with regulatory requirements.

The importance of gas drying. Drying gas is essential for ensuring its quality and purity before utilizing it in various applications. The importance of efficient gas drying processes cannot be overstated, as moisture and impurities in the gas can cause damage to equipment, pipeline corrosion, and reduced energy efficiency.

Gas drying operations are associated with problems such as inaccurate humidity measurement, fluctuations in gas composition, different flow rates, problems with temperature control, compliance with regulatory requirements, as well as problems with maintenance and reliability of equipment.

Improvement of control mechanisms. The introduction of advanced control systems, such as distributed control systems (DCS) or programmable logic controllers (PLC), allows monitoring, data analysis and automated control of gas drying parameters in real time. By using these systems, the process's efficiency, reliability, and safety are enhanced.

Advanced sensors that measure humidity, temperature, pressure, and flow are integrated to provide accurate data for precise control and optimization of gas drying processes. IoT-enabled sensors offer the capability of real-time data analysis and predictive analytics.

Technological advances in the field of gas drying. Introduction of membrane technology. The introduction of membrane-based dewatering systems offers benefits such as lower energy consumption, smaller footprint, and greater reliability than conventional methods like absorption or adsorption.

Preventive maintenance, early fault detection, and optimization of gas drying processes are possible with the integration of intelligent monitoring devices, control algorithms, and machine learning, which increases overall reliability and productivity.

Maintenance and reliability improvement. Minimizing downtime and extending the service life of the equipment during gas drying can be achieved by implementing preventive maintenance strategies like regular inspections, lubrication, and component replacement.

The application of reliability design principles such as failure Mode and Consequence Analysis (FMEA) and reliability-oriented maintenance (RCM) improves the reliability of critical systems and components by reducing the number of unforeseen failures.

Conclusion: Optimizing efficiency, reliability, and safety in gas drying processes requires the improvement of control mechanisms and compliance with regulatory requirements. Industrial enterprises can achieve operational excellence and contribute to sustainable energy in the future by using advanced technologies, regulatory compliance measures, and best practices. Regulatory control and compliance mechanisms will be further improved through continued research and development in the field of gas drying technologies, automation, predictive analytics, and sustainability initiatives. Innovation and continuous improvement of gas drying processes will be facilitated through cooperation between industry stakeholders, regulators, and technology providers.

References

1. N.R.Yusupbekov, B.I.Muhamedov, Sh.M.G‘ulomov Texnologik jarayonlarni nazorat qilish va avtomatlashtirish 2012.
2. N.X. ERMATOV, D.G‘. AZIZOVA, N.M. AVLAYAROVA, B.Yu. NOMOZOV, R.S. BEKJONOV, A.I. ABDIRAZAKOV, M.X. ASHUROV. KONDA NEFT, GAZ, SUVNI YIG‘ISH, TAYYORLASH VA TASHISH // UO‘K: 533.98:551.577.54(075)
3. Н. М. Шумский, О. Б. Грынив, К. А. Шумская. Основные способы осушки газа. // Молодой учёный. – 2019 – №24 (262).
4. М.М. Кручин. Способ адсорбционной очистки осушки и очистки природного газа. - 2024. // РОССИЯ. – 2019 – 7.
5. Л.Ш. Махмудова, Х.Х. Ахмадова, Ж. Т. Хадисова, З.А. Абдулмежидова, Э.У. Идрисова. ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ОСУШКИ ПРИРОДНОГО ГАЗА АДСОРБЦИОННЫМ И АДСОРБЦИОННЫМ МЕТОДАМИ. // Вестник ГГНТУ. – 2020.27.16.0.3.

